

Effects of Teamwork Team Trust and Training on Employee Performance: The Moderating Role of Team Member Exchange

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Abstract

This research aims to investigate the effect of teamwork, team trust, and training on employee performance and how team-member exchange (TMX) moderates the relationship between teamwork, team trust, training, and employee performance. The analysis was done through Smart-PLS 3.0 using 210 responses collected from the employees of SMEs. The results show that teamwork, team trust, and training have a significant effect on employee performance, and team member exchange moderates the relationship between teamwork, team trust, and employee performance. This further helps team members to share the knowledge with others and lead towards creativity and they tend to create novelty in their work through learning from others' mistakes as well. This ultimately accelerates employee performance. However, it is found that team member exchange does not moderate the relationship between training and employee performance. These findings suggest that the management of SMEs in developing countries like Pakistan should encourage a culture of teamwork and team trust in the organizations. This study helps to understand the management of SMEs in the generalizability of the positive relationship of teamwork, team-trust,

and training and employee performance in the SME's of Pakistan

Keywords: Teamwork, Team trust, Training, Team member exchange, Employee performance, SME.

Introduction:

Teams in organizations now-a-days are one of the most highlighted topic going around the world. Most of the organizations face different problems which is normally too multifaceted for one employee or individual to handle it single handedly (Lombardo & Roddy, 2010). No doubt, the effort of the employees oblige as the input to the organizational objectives which can be further observed as performance in the form of output (Adil & Ab Hamid, 2020). And this performance of the employee reveals the occupational behavior which must be parallel or dependable to the values and core objectives of the organization which normally can be observed with the attainment of organizational goals by the employees (Mulki, Caemmerer, & Heggde, 2015). As per previous studies, work has been done on topics like: Teamwork, Team Trust, Training and Employee performance. Adil and Ab Hamid (2020) discussed how the teamwork effects the performance of the employees and how a supervisor as moderator effect the relationship of teamwork and the employee performance measured through cross-sectional study. Further results displayed, the teamwork has a substantial and positive impact on employee performance (P- Value = 0.308; T-Value = 4.523) in the high-tech the relationship exhibit an f-square value of 0.081 display the magnitude of result according to population. The supervisor as a moderator support the relationship of teamwork and employee performance, it strengthen the positive relationship among them and resulted as increase in performance of the employees. Whereas, I. Ahmad and Manzoor (2017) debated about the relationship of teamwork, training and employee empowerment on employee performance and the findings were training considered as very much significant and have strong relationship with employee performance. Regression coefficient R shows value of .697 which indicated 69.7% relationship occurs between teamwork, training and employee performance and coefficient of determination (R²) was 0.485 which implied that 48.5% of variation in employee performance. Teamwork, and training described 27.8% and 49% variation in employee performance and the organization must implement these practices to improve the overall productivity of the organization to compete in market and to gain competitive edge. However Phina, Arinze, Chidi, and Chukwuma (2018) conferred the effect of team member abilities, team member esprit de corps, and team trust on employee performance.

When employee achieves his/her required task and job duties is titled as employee performance and stated as output of the quality, efficiency and effectiveness of their work which represent the degree of worth employee have in organization. In other words, the ability or the ambition of an employee to work hard and better to accomplish the organizational objectives on time constitute as task performance (Adil & Ab Hamid, 2020). Team define a group of people established to perform a task collectively and the teams in organizations normally comprise of employees who attain some specific skills to fulfill required objectives of the organization. During this procedure, team members have chance to learn as well as communicate from each other to perform tasks proficiently and professionally (Hanaysha, 2016b).

Similarly, organizations have implemented the culture of teamwork to achieve goals more

effectively and efficiently, and teamwork has been viewed as the activities done by the employees collectively to accomplish goals or objectives by retaining the interests of all the members to that of the group interest as whole (Hanaysha, 2016b). Organizations of modern era increasingly using teamwork as compared to the old organizations and in public and private sectors or even in the non-profit sector teamwork is preferably increasing and they are more supportive towards the teamwork, empowerment and the collaboration among the teams of the employees (Eisenberger et al., 2010). Now-a-days, organizations are more active to improve the performance of the employees and gain competitive advantage, these organizations are training their employees to get more productive, imaginative to increase the performance (Falola, Osibanjo, & Ojo, 2014). Training can be defined as learning process in which the primary emphasis is to gain the knowledge, classifying the rules, increasing and improving the skills, enhancing behavior of the employee to increase the employee performance in the organization to gain competitive edge or competitive advantage (Sabir, Akhtar, Bukhari, Nasir, & Ahmed, 2014). Carrying out training and its implementation is a practical issue through which employees learn new skills and knowledge for the growth in employee performance, it also increase the loyalty and commitment within employees towards their organization (Nkosi, 2015). Learning have significant relationship with that of positive outcome (D'Amato & Herzfeldt, 2008; Lin & Chang, 2005; Millar, Gitsham, Bozer, Sarros, & Santora, 2013; VandeWalle, 2001). Moreover, the teamwork can only be done when the support of team members develop the unique skill and understanding and coordination among them in the form of trust (Erdem & Ozen, 2003). Trust causes the development of the team and the behavioral foundation of teamwork, which further results in the increase of the performance of employees in organizations (Mickan & Rodger, 2000). This study rotates around the performance of the employees and these employees of organizations are one of the vital asset of any organization. According to the previous studies, theoretical relationships between the variables teamwork, team trust, and training and employee performance are available separately however, there was still a gap which need to be found if empirical evidence of these relations in the context of SME's of developing countries such as Pakistan. Alongside, literature suggest that team member exchange has positive effect on the performance of the employees which shows that employees are more expected to perform better in such cases or situations if they receive intangible assistance from their team members. This study can contribute in the body of knowledge in literature. But the question remained in the middle of nowhere, whether TMX strengthen the relationships between teamwork and employee performance, team trust and employee performance, & training and employee performance.

Literature Review:

The main focus of the literature review is to analyze the research gap and explore the relationships between teamwork, team trust and training on employee performance with the synergy of or the moderating variable of team member exchange. These relationships can be applied within the SME's looking forward to improve the performance of the employees to gain the competitive advantage in the market.

Teamwork: Teamwork or work group was introduced decades ago as autonomous work group and social-technical systems (Trist & Bamforth, 1951). Teamwork has been described

by many researchers as, combined efforts of people to achieve one goal effectively and efficiently, teamwork is the desire of members of the team to work or involve in social dealings and cooperate among them to complete interdependent tasks (Lankau, 1997), upholding relationship within a team (Mathieu, Maynard, Rapp, & Gilson, 2008), and constructing adherence to work with other team members, as well as augmenting interpersonal relations within team and increasing commitment within team objectives (Watson, Johnson, & Merritt, 1998). Teamwork comprises of a cluster of the people working collectively to achieve a common or desired goal (Ooko, 2013).

Organizations in new era are competing globally and the continuity have been seen in shifting towards the teamwork to leverage the knowledge, information as well as in the resources (Gordon, 2002; Jaca, Viles, Tanco, Mateo, & Santos, 2013). The concept of teamwork is becoming more popular in modern organizations especially in enhancing the organizational commitment and productivity within employees and also been proven previously that teamwork provide aid to fulfill the need of team members within organization (Adebanjo & Kehoe, 2001). Teamwork described as joint effort of the employees to accomplish a shared goal by ignoring individual interest and providing more worth to the collective interest of overall team (Hanaysha, 2016a). The core of the teamwork is to adopt the methods of reduction and breaking of the workload into pieces or dividing of the workload among team members of a team so they can participate to accomplish a goal or objective in to pieces (AlArafat & Doblas, 2020). Employees working in such teams where teamwork is the first priority these employees are more confident and strengthen their information to improve their skills which results in levitation of performance and enhancement of work level (Al Salman & Hassan, 2016).

In the SME's the higher management need to understand that work teams are normally built on a diversification of members from different incumbencies and emotional needs and these specialized teams exchange their knowledge to fulfil the targets within team by working on it together as team members, which contribute towards organizational sustainability, effectiveness and gain the competitive edge within SME's (Adil & Ab Hamid, 2020). Many researchers approved that the goals of the organizations can be achieved by the individuals but chief triumph have been attained by teams through their teamwork. And the teamwork is conjoint efforts in which each individual provide his/her energy and asses as team effectiveness (I. Ahmad & Manzoor, 2017). The involvement and the commitment among employees of any organization directly linked with teamwork consider the key of Japanese efficiency (Silos, 1999). By sharing knowledge, skills and being supple to work for multiple goals in the interest of common goal in cooperative environment indicates teamwork which can expand the output of employees collectively. Hence, the employees working in teams become the standard of the organization (Phina et al., 2018). The performance of the individuals and the organization can be improved through teamwork but it need to be cherished time to time (Ingram, 1996). Teamwork, empowerment and the collaboration are more preferred in public, private and non-profit organizations in modern era (Eisenberger et al., 2010).

Team-trust: When teams develop the confidence among each other's capabilities helps to cultivate trust which simply signifies, relying on each other in team for the accomplishment of accurate goal and feel responsible as team and this trust among team members cultivate

coordination within team members and unique skills and abilities (Erdem & Ozen, 2003). The platform from where employees of an organization or members of a team make bounds of faith are good reasons and the availability of knowledge (McAllister, 1995). Two-way trust enable collaboration between the team members (Langton, Robbins, & Judge, 2013). Teams with high level of trust or teams which provide more trust to the members of the team are more tolerant and accept novel and divergent ideas to work on and heard by other members to trust on a team member (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; McAllister, 1995). Hence, trust as a facilitator and promoter of joint relationships within employees or members of a team which seeks towards more collaborative environment (Abrams, Cross, Lesser, & Levin, 2003; Middel, Boer, & Fisscher, 2006; Russ, McNeilly, Comer, & Light, 1998).

In an organizational environment where it meant to have confidence in supremacy of belief, honesty and trust in employees to create innovative ideas, they normally focus on the attainment eventual goals instead of individuality (Aydin & Ceylan, 2009). It is mentioned previously that, in teams when member of the team trust each other it provide them impression of security, thus helping in feeding energy in innovation and recognition rather than defending oneself (Gibb, 1978). Therefore, Trust is meant to believe that others will act as expected and will not be unscrupulous (Jarvenpaa, Knoll, & Leidner, 1998). Team trust has been also described as, the degree of confidence of an individual and eager to take action by the words, movements and decisions taken by other employee (Kanawattanachai & Yoo, 2002).

Hence, the trust within team members shows open communication and tolerance regardless of principle leads to mutual understanding (Smith & Barclay, 1997).

According to the Wilderom, Wouters, and van Brussel (2007), team trust actually effects the confidence of all the team members on each other to achieve the goals in their organization and to share their success within their teams.

Training: To cope up with human resources training is one of the most important activity in an organization, the work headlining by the employees through learning programs which are specifically supported by scientific theories in a meaning way which includes efficiency, effectiveness and individual's variances (Diab & Ajlouni, 2015). Similarly, training in other words described as a learning process which consists of gaining of knowledge, modification of behavior, considering rules and refining skills to improve employee performance (Sabir et al., 2014). The organizations which encourages trainings for their departments and teams within the organizations results in additionally committed employees (Hanif, 2013). Training was defined, a strategic and methodical effort to amend or to cultivate knowledge, skills and attitudes through a process of educating employee or polishing capabilities to attain effective performance to perform a task or a bundle of tasks (Garavan, 1997). Training however, can be conveyed through different methods some of them are; on-job training, training through videos, online courses. Whereas, most of the organizations provide tailored training to their employees according to their and organizational need (Ismail, 2016). Those organizations which normally invest in trainings and helps employees to progress and to improve their skills and capabilities ends up with better performance (Úbeda-García, Marco-Lajara, Sabater-Sempere, & Garcia-Lillo, 2013). Training provide employees with particular skills needed to achieve goal and help them to overcome the deficiencies in their performance (Poh & Abd Hamid, 2001). However, training accelerate improvement in skills which further leads

to high assurance side by side, sense of be appropriate and well-being which results in organizational competitiveness (Acton & Golden, 2002; Karia, 1999). Hence, when employees of any organization go through training and development programs, it automatically boost their confidence and motivate them to get involve more intensely in their jobs (Paradise, 2008). Training is essential to

obtain the goals successfully and also essential for personnel goals (Stone & Stone, 2013). Organizations which prefer to provide high level of trainings to their employees recognized that their organizations gain profit thrice as compare to their competitors (Jaoude, 2015). Furthermore, trainings should be according to the market need and this can be cover by identifying the skills needed by the employees and specifically for the job, this is how training can be aligned according to the motivation, specialized skills and transferring critical thinking skills to the employees of the organizations (Halawi & Haydar, 2018). SME's can gain competitive edge through the performance of the employees as high-performing market-driven business organizations believe in investment on human capital for their trainings which boost their personal and organizational growth and success (Adil & Ab Hamid, 2020). Employee Performance: Performance is described as, attainment of goals in specific situation by skilled employees effectively and efficiently (Prasetya & Kato, 2011). Employee performance has been defined as, accomplishing tasks well-defined by any organization and appraising these on the bases of the performance against defined performance standards given to the employees considered as employee performance (Chen, 2011). The result or the outcome of the task performed efficiently and responsibly without interfering any law in organization to accomplish organizational goal called performance (N. Ahmad, Iqbal, Javed, & Hamad, 2014). The productivity of the employee and the results of employee development which eventually affect the effectiveness of that specific organization in which employee is working called as employee performance (Hameed & Waheed, 2011). Employee performance depict, how effectively and efficiently or poorly employee behave in the organization or at the workplace and also describe, how well they complete their job duties or accomplish their targets implied by the organization in the light of performance targets and helps to minimalize the wastage (Camilleri, 2020).

Accordingly, it has been argued that many organizations use rating scale to evaluate the capabilities and efficiency of the employees to estimate the employee performance level (Darden & Babin, 1994). And satisfied employees with their job have high performance and those who are not happy face retention (Trumbo, 1976). Employees with high performance seem to be happy and satisfied and easy to motivate high performers to attain goals (Kreitner, Kinicki, & Buelens, 1999). Similarly, happiness of employees is about work allied responsibilities upturn the performance in better way (Robbins & Judge, 2007). Work which is completed efficiently and with quality as well as quantity by any employee according to job, responsibilities is employee performance (N. Ahmad et al., 2014). Employee performance is necessary for overall society, it aids to create equilibrium within economy as it increases the living standards of employees by increase in their salaries due which utilization of goods increases (Griffin, Welsh, & Moorhead, 1981; Seers, 1989).

Team Member Exchange: The perception of the individual within a team about the relationship with the peer group as whole is considered (Seers, 1989). This type of side by side give-and-take relationship is defined in the framework of work group for the continue

interaction between mutually dependent members as a whole set (Katz & Kahn, 1978). In return to the relation this group strengthens by actions (Jacobs, 1971). And the result of this strengthening members of the group varies in their abilities, interests, needs and demands unite together in group as a whole. Hence, the team member exchange has been defined as the willingness of a member to assist and support other members, and to share ideas and feedback in return and in turn information, help, recognition are received from the other member of team, and this process shows the how effective relationship is within the team (Seers, 1989).

Investigation shows that team member exchange actually arise from the association of members within a team with the attainment through the efficiency of group construction (Seers, Petty, & Cashman, 1995). The concept of the team member exchange or TMX consist according to the social exchange theory's fundamental assumptions which includes two types of relations and those are economic and social (P. M. Blau, 1964). It definitely depends on the quality of team member exchange, as high level of TMX relationship refers towards the high level of social exchange simultaneously the team members will be more willing to share the information within their teams, groups or even with their peers through which they provide required support and recognition as well, whereas on the contrary, low level of TMX includes like economical exchange which leads toward short period of relationship (Liu, Loi, & Lam, 2011). More importantly, when SME's struggles for effective learning, they need their managers to obtain, create and broadcast or share their knowledge or the success of their organizations for competitive advantage (Adil & Ab Hamid, 2020). Liden, Wayne, and Sparrowe (2000) said, high level of TMX raise mutual care, support and feedback from the colleagues which consider furthermore the requirement for job completion. TMX has been described as the exchange of the relationships among the team members in terms of sharing novel ideas, giving feedback to each other's, sharing energies, resources, expertise, and acknowledgement between an employee and his/ her peers as a group (Seers, 1989; Seers et al., 1995). As compared to the traditional work teams, the teams connected with high quality of TMX are more satisfied within the teams and coworkers, supplement high job satisfaction and high team cohesiveness (Farmer, Van Dyne, & Kamdar, 2015; Seers et al., 1995). Certainly, high quality of TMX within the group or team than the members of this team will experience wisdom of strong affinity (Nougarou, 2017).

Hypothesis Development & Theoretical Model:

This study incorporates a positivist approach within the theory of Social exchange theory. the reciprocity among the members of a team represent the quality of TMX and high quality of TMX relationship described as social exchange in which team members are willing to share information with their team, peers and groups for the necessary assistance and recognition (Farh, Lanaj, & Ilies, 2017; Liu et al., 2011).

Teamwork and Employee Performance: To enhance employee performance team work is an essential practice in any organization (Adil & Ab Hamid, 2020). Teamwork is vital part of any organizational life cycle which is also modern and conspicuous feature (Mijakoski et al., 2018). Similarly, members are responsible for performance goals working together in a team (Ancona, 1996). During teamwork, members get different ideas which helps to lower down the cost, bring up innovation in products or management for instance, help in time saving, able to provide better quality, enhance the experiences of services and many

more to gain the competitive edge (Adil, 2015; Porter, 2008). As it is argued that, high level of performance intensely governed by hard work of an employee (Jaramillo, Ladik, Marshall, & Mulki, 2007). Working within a team, the team members also permit the co-workers to identify the importance of the teamwork and also clarify and succor them so they can enhance their performance (AlArafat & Doblaz, 2020). Whereas, team members not only work together collectively but also have disputes among them that's the reason team work considered as complex phenomenon (Hoegl & Parboteeah, 2007).

Teamwork consider as a strategy which has advantage to improve performance of an employee and even the organization (Ingram, 1996). Else, creativity and innovation can achieve easily and considerably through teamwork (Hoegl & Parboteeah, 2007), for example; organizational performance (I. Ahmad & Manzoor, 2017) and product designing (Kichuk & Wiesner, 1997). Enhancement or increase in the performance of employees and solving problems with high productivity and capability depends on the presence of effective teamwork (Banwo, Du, & Onokala, 2015).

H1: Teamwork has significant positive effect on the employee performance.

Team trust and Employee Performance: when team members cultivate confidence among each other and on their competencies create trust among them and this trust develop unique skills and coordination (Erdem & Ozen, 2003). Jointly trust or interpersonal trust is major key among the team members of any team to facilitate cooperation (Robbins & Judge, 2007). Positive relation has been found between teamwork and the employee performance (Mickan & Rodger, 2000). The employee must accountable cultivate trust within organization and this trust implement by the organization to provide synergetic environment to the teams to work in organization and also transfer this trust for measuring performance appraisal toindorse positive organizational morals (Erdem & Ozen, 2003). Trust is a construct that provides environment in organizations among team members where they can openly discuss new ideas, mistakes, share feeling, accept criticism which improve them develop more synergy (Edmondson, 1999). Team members who work together with excessive cooperation and also share information with each other and expect in turn as well, steer them towards high performance (Larson & LaFasto, 1989). Trust is needed by the teams more as compared to the individuals and the reason behind it is interdependency at high level is compulsory to complete tasks and goals (Whitener, Brodt, Korsgaard, & Werner, 1998). According to the Phina et al. (2018), team trust have the higher coefficient of .650 which describe the increase in the performance of the employees through the team trust within team. Thus, the hypothesis suggested according to the above discussion is;

H2: Team trust has momentous positive effect on employee performance.

Training and Employee performance: Training has been defined as, a process in which employee learn and improve their understanding, capabilities and abilities which are needed to accomplish organizational goals (Gallie, Zhou, Felstead, & Green, 2009). Trainings are given by the organizations to their employees to achieve gain some skills and abilities to accomplish organizational goals or objectives (Cole, 2002). For the better results, organizations provide necessary programs needed by the employees and organization (Boudreau, Gefen, & Straub, 2001; Partlow, 1996; Tihanyi, 2000). Therefore, in training process the main focus is to gain knowledge, enhance behaviors of the employees, recognizing rules of organization, improvement and learning new skills are involved to

increase employee performance (Sabir et al., 2014). To manage the employee performance, training contemplate to empowering employees to attain tasks with the time span effectively and efficiently (Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Galbraith & Lawler, 1993). Performance of the employees in organizations is very important, whereas the success of the organization depends upon the creativity, innovation and training of the employees which facilitate employees to improve their performance (Men, 2015). Nowadays, training is considered as crucial part of the organization which helps employees to perform well, they are trained to be creative, productive and imaginative that will further leads them to improve their performance and gain competitive advantage (Falola et al., 2014). Else, training have vital positive relationship between managerial results, training and HRM (Purcell, 2003). It has been argued previously, that training and employee performance have significant positive relation (Elnaga & Imran, 2013). According to the Harrison (2000), organizational performance as well as employee performance can be prejudiced through trainings and has been considered to be the key factor in attaining the organizational objective or goals.

The increase in the training will results in the increase of employee performance and the organizational performance (I. Ahmad & Manzoor, 2017). According to the Dermal and Čater (2013), the attainment of new skills and knowledge through training leads to improvement in the employee performance.

Hence, to fill the gap training programs are the best solution due to which employee performance can be improved through standard and actual performance (Swart, Mann, Brown, & Price, 2012). Training is consist strategically, which educate Human resources which further leads towards high level of competencies and efficacy through development to improve the performance of the employees (Ameen1, 2, & Baharom, 2019). Trainings has numerous effects on the employee performance which includes consolidation of the relationship among the employees, refining attitudes, development of sense of belongings, rumpling the performance of the employees, constancy towards the organization, reduction in absenteeism as well as reduction in turnover rate (Al-qout, 2017). On the basis of above discussion, the hypothesis is below:

H3: Training has significant positive effect on employee performance.

TMX as moderator within Teamwork and Employee Performance: The team member exchange as a construct was originate to monologue towards the exchange relationship within peer group as team (Seers, 1989). Data depicts the level of reciprocity among team members through their teamwork (Seers et al., 1995). Workflow through joint relation within the teams is key factor of teamwork's middling level of team member exchange quality (Thompson, 1967). High quality of team member exchange help employees to achieve beyond the expectations through mutual care, support and feedback from his/her peer which results in high employee performance (Liden et al., 2000).

Particularly, the exchange of socio-economic resources such as recognition and support from the team member motivate him/her to add on more efforts to achieve high level of job performance (Liu et al., 2011) without TMX it is very difficult to achieve high level of performance by employee (Seers, 1989). The employees with the higher TMX reported as better performer (Farh et al., 2017). Thus, on the bases of above discussion the hypothesis is written below;

H4: TMX has significant positive effect on the relationship of teamwork and employee

performance.

TMX as moderator within Team-trust & Employee Performance: Trust has been always linked in different activities at workplace at individual level, within teams and even at the organizational level (Li, Li, Feng, Liu, & Tsai, 2019; Tourigny, Han, Baba, & Pan, 2019). The high level of TMX results in high level of trust among team members of a team (Yukl, 1989). It has been described, when employees trust on their subordinates or team members they share information and their experiences with them (McAllister, 1995). The variation of TMX is found in relationship, as with the mutual understanding when information and experiences are shared within teams it provide a sense of mutual commitment, obligation and trust among the team members (Seers, 1989). Trust among the team members enhances the TMX (Schermuly & Meyer, 2016). High quality TMX leads to trust, commitment, mutuality, common interests and shared values and results in workplace friendships (Chiu, Hsu, & Wang, 2006). And higher level of TMX results in better performance of the employee (Seers, 1989).

The concept of the TMX consist according to the social exchange theory's fundamental assumptions which includes two types of relations and those are economic and social (P. Blau, 1964). Similarly, socio-emotional exchange with team members, such as support and recognition, can motivate the team members to work hard to achieve high level of job performance (Liu et al., 2011). According to the Li et al. (2019), high quality of TMX have an element of mutual trust which describe the belief of team members that they will not be exploited by their team and with mutual trust they are more enthusiastic to share their contacts and information within teams within organization. Thus, according to the literature the hypothesis is given below;

H5: TMX has significant positive effect on the relationship of team trust and employee performance.

TMX as moderator within Training & Employee Performance: Training has been always considered as the source of human development which results in the form of advantages and benefits for employee as well as for the organization (Aguinis & Kraiger, 2009). Many scholars consider training as investment which justify according to the financial returns (Balkin & Richebé, 2007). It is ponder as a tool to increase employee productivity and improve employee performance (Madera, Steele, & Beier, 2011). The organizations which prefers to improve planning and training programs executions they are more tend to achieve high level of performance (Jehanzeb, Rasheed, & Rasheed, 2013). Training helps in learning new skills and also strengthen the capabilities of the employees to enhance their performance (Palo & Padhi, 2003).

However, providing training according to the requirement build-up-time, enhance efficiency and improve productivity will leads toward the expansion in the performance (Kellie, 1999). Whereas, Nkosi (2015) indicated that training have positive effect of the enhancement of the performance of employee. TMX represent the relationships among the subordinates and team and these changes are to discover through the result of employees' socialization those are consider in the form of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, employee turnover and the employee performance (Kim, Lee, & Carlson, 2010). And team member exchange is strongly connected with key factor of organization that are performance, commitment and innovation (Monica Hu, Ou, Chiou, & Lin, 2012). According to the Seers (1989), as higher the

level of TMX results in high level of employee performance. Thus, according to the literature the hypothesis is given below;

H6: TMX has significant positive effect on the relationship of training and employee performance.

Theoretical Framework:

This study focuses on the background of how teamwork, team trust, training has positive effect on the employee performance. It helped us to understand how these variable cause effect on the performance of the employees working in an organization during this whole process. This study also helps the upper management of SME's in developing countries like Pakistan the importance of working in teams and enhancing the employee performance. Further how team member exchange as moderator effects the relationships between teamwork and employee performance, team trust and employee performance, training and employee performance and what will be the level of abide within these relations.

Following figure represents the study model in which teamwork, team trust and training are the IV's, which effects on the dependent variable or DV that is employee performance. Whereas, team member exchange (TMX) is playing its role as moderator in between the relationships of teamwork and employee performance, team trust and employee performance, & training and employee performance.

Research Methodology:

The conduction of the research is to clarify the measurement of the impact on employee performance through the teamwork, team-trust and training and analyze the moderation of TMX between the relationships of; a) teamwork and employee performance, b) team trust and employee performance. It includes Target population, sampling design & Data collection tool, place of study, nature of study, unit of analysis and data analyzing software. The target population encompassed of the employees of SME's, which were based in Pakistan. The basic unit of analyses were employees of SME's. The contribution in such organizations in Pakistan will benefit to grow economy. Therefore, the positivism philosophy has been followed and the nature of the study was "Causal". A list of people in the form of hardcopy or soft through which the sample size is selected is called sample frame. The total number of the SME's in Pakistan is 1000 SME's (Business, 2021). A sample size was the population selected from the sample frame to conduct survey. The sample size was 278 firms of the sample frame of 1000 firms at 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level (Business, 2021). The sample size was calculated through the formula derived by Krejcie and Morgan (Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. 1970). Simple random sampling was conducted in collecting data through quantitative method. For the quantitative method, the questionnaire was prepared by adopting items of variables from different platforms which were contemplated appropriate to measure the variables. The link of Google form was shared through emails (collected from websites) of organizations. For the expediency, the questionnaire has been attached in the end after references. The items were measured through the "5-point likert scale". However, only 210 individuals responded to questionnaires sent to them. The instrument was adopted and its description is given below in the table 3.1 Analysis was done through SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) and the Smart PLS 3.0.

Sr.	Variable	Author	No. of Items
1	Employee Performance	(Jerobon, 2016)	4 Items
2	Teamwork	(Anderson-Butcher et al., 2014)	10 Items
3	Team trust	(Pinjani & Palvia, 2013)	4 Items
4	Training	(Lawler, Mohrman, & Ledford, 1992)	5 Items
5	Team Member Exchange	(Chae, Seo, & Lee, 2015)	6 Items

(Table number)

Results and Discussion:

The analysis and the stimulating results has been discussed which includes Hypothesis testing and demographics. This section highlights validity and reliability of the variables and their items. The information collected of the individuals who responded to the questionnaire including gender, qualification, age, job designation, total experience, current job tenure, size of the firm and Monthly income. Below table demonstrate the summary of the respondents' information the division has been done according to the individuals' gender, age, qualification, experience, job tenure, firm size, designation and income who responded to the questionnaire is shown in the below table (table no). The total sample of 210 has been categorized into four categories; male, female, transgender and not to prefer. The male were higher in preponderance with percentage of 70.5% and females are 29.0 percent, whereas prefer not to say was only 0.5 percent. The age assortment between 26-32 with the highest

percentage of 54.3% respondents, at the age scale of 47 and Above the respondents responded were the least as it was only 5.2% only. Master’s Degree Holder respondents were higher in percentage of 47.1% and in the last option that is Doctoral Degree Holder were only 1.4 percent. This table also display that respondents who has responded from 4-12 years of experience bracket holders were higher in percentage of 43.8% and the respondents who responded according the current job tenure within 2-5 current job tenure in years of bracket display the higher percentage of 48.6%. The responses were 26.2% from small, 64.3 percent were from medium and whereas 9.5% were from large firms. The respondents who responded towards the Middle management were according to the percentage of 21.9% and the respondents who responded towards the Supervisor/Team Leader were 23.8 percent. In the end, the respondents who responded towards the bracket “51,000 and Above” respondents who responded were 65.0%.

Demographic profile of the respondents

	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Gender			
Female	61	29.0	29.0
Male	148	70.5	99.5
Not to Prefer	1	0.5	100.0
Total	210	100.0	
Age			
18-25	35	16.7	16.7
26-32	114	54.3	71.0
33-39	38	18.1	89.0
40-46	12	5.7	94.8
47 and Above	11	5.2	100.0
Total	210	100.0	
Qualification			
SSC (Matric/O-level)	3	1.4	1.4
HSSC (Intermediate/O-Level)	14	6.7	8.1
Bachelor's Holder	Degree 91	43.3	51.4
Master's Holder	Degree 99	47.1	98.6
Doctoral Holder	Degree 3	1.4	100.0
Total	210	100.0	
Experience (In Years)			
1-3	79	37.6	37.6

4-12	92	43.8	81.4
13-22	24	11.4	92.9
23-32	10	4.8	97.6
33 and Above	5	2.4	100.0
Total	210	100.0	
Current Job Tenure			
0-1	59	28.1	28.1
2-5	102	48.6	76.7
6-8	29	13.8	90.5
9-12	9	4.3	94.8
13 and Above	11	5.2	100.0
Total	210	100.0	
Size of the Firm			
Small (Less than 10)	55	26.2	26.2
Medium (11 to 50)	135	64.3	90.5
Large (50+)	20	9.5	100.0
Total	210	100.0	
Designation			
Top Management	41	19.5	19.5
Middle Management	46	21.9	41.4
Supervisor/Team Leader	50	23.8	65.2
Team Member	36	17.1	82.4
Employee	35	16.7	99.0
Other	2	1.0	100.0
Total	210	100.0	
Monthly Income			
Less than 20,000	5	2.4	2.4
20,000-30,000	25	11.9	14.3
31,000-40,000	19	9.0	23.3
41,000-50,000	24	11.4	34.8
51,000 and Above	137	65.2	100.0
Total	210	100.0	

Reliability & Validity Testing:

The reliability defined as, consistency and the dependability or the probability of any service, method, product or test which will perform its function sufficiently according to the environment. Whereas, validity defined as the accuracy of the results obtained according to what they supposed to measure. So, to conduct the algorithm for reliability testing, 300 iterations has been selected with the factor as its weightage scheme and Criterion stop (10^{-X}) was selected as 7 and run the software on the model. The reliability of indicators confirms the commonality among them which is measured by the constructs. So in the beginning of the analysis, reliability and validity of the constructs were enthralled.

Bollen (1984) & Nunnally (1978), that Cronbach Alpha is more significant at the value of 0.7

or above which represent that the measurement of model is reliable. And rendering to the advance research, the reliability is consider when if lies within the value of 0.70 and 0.90. Whereas, below 0.6 value depicts lacking in reliability (Afthanorhan, 2013). However, the values between 0.6 and 0.7 pondered as satisfactory composite reliability measuring scale. Conversely, if value is 0.95 or greater than that, it portrays that the results are not appreciable because the indicators of specific construct has been measured the same phenomena repeatedly (Bollen, 1984). According to the current study, the CR value or composite reliability values are perfect as compare to the threshold. Whereas, rho is also considered as a good measurement value according to the SEM as it is based on loadings as compared to the correlations. And it can be seen in the table 4.9 that Cronbach Alpha's as greater than 0.7 value so it was considered as reliable conferring to the scale and items. The validity has been checked with the reliability as well. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) shows the "convergent validity" in the above table. It display the perfection of the indicators of the constructs load or their convergent value on specific constructs which describe the variance of the indicators (Chin, 1998). The convergent validity extracted through the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) (Nunnally, 1978).

The researchers believe that the Statistics of AVE must be above than 0.5 value in the case of reflective construct. According to this study, the values of AVE is higher than 0.5 as it can be seen in the above table. These values in the above table displays that the convergent validity of the data is really good.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	CR	AVE
EP	0.836	0.841	0.890	0.670
TMX	0.926	0.933	0.942	0.731
TT	0.907	0.919	0.935	0.782
TW	0.914	0.918	0.927	0.561
TR	0.852	0.862	0.894	0.627

Outer Loading:

The outer loading of the reflective indicators can be seen table below. All the values of the indicators are greater than 0.70 which are acceptable and in fact they all are acceptable. The below table 4.10 shows the outer loadings of indicators are greater than 0.7 and none of the indicator was removed from the model as their Cronbach Alpha were greater than 0.7 as well. So, none of the indicator need to be excluded from the model.

EP	Description	Loading	VIF
EP1	"Employees encourage each other to perform their duties"	0.832	1.807
EP2	"Employee give each other the maximum support needed to do their duties"	0.816	1.842
EP3	"Employees in the organization embrace team work in their duties"	0.787	1.705

EP4	“Supervisors of the employees have a good cordial relationship with their juniors”	0.837	1.960
TMX1	“Team members encourage each other to improve their work performance”	0.865	2.779
TMX2	“The high quality of the relationships in the team makes members enthusiastic about their work and the atmosphere keeps them focused on their work all day long”	0.860	2.796
TMX3	“The interaction among team members is good”	0.901	3.962
TMX4	“I often ask others for help”	0.828	2.535
TMX5	“Members on this team willingly suggest better work methods to others”	0.813	2.292
TMX6	“Other members on this team recognize my potential”	0.860	2.864
To what extent do you receive training on the following skills?			
TR1	“Group decision making/ problem solving skills”	0.803	2.370
TR2	“Leadership skills”	0.851	1.862
TR3	“Skills in understanding the business (accounting, management, finance, etc.)”	0.757	1.658
TR4	“Team-building skills”	0.759	1.628
TR5	“Job-skills training”	0.787	3.366
TT1	“Overall, the people in my team are very trustworthy”	0.923	2.551
TT2	“We are usually considerate of one another’s feelings on this team”	0.866	3.304
TT3	“The people in my team are friendly”	0.904	2.209
TT4	“I can rely on other members of my team”	0.843	2.373
TW1	“I think that teamwork is important”	0.751	2.583
TW2	“People who work in teams can learn more than if they work by themselves”	0.740	2.112
TW3	“I feel confident in my ability to work in a team”	0.730	2.158
TW4	“I know how to give my team members feedback that will not hurt their feelings”	0.774	1.841
TW5	“I ask others for feedback”	0.762	1.949
TW6	“I make an effort to include other members of my group”	0.724	2.728
TW7	“I value the contributions of my team members”	0.700	2.067
TW8	“I treat my team members as equal members of the team”	0.793	2.612
TW9	“I am good at communication with my team members”	0.730	
TW10	“I feel confident in my ability to be a leader”	0.782	

Discriminant Validity:

The indicators of the latent construct must have higher loading value as compare to the other constructs. The Factor consist of the indicators analyze its validity to confirm the quality of the valid items. The indication of the factor which represent one item as “valid item” depicts the good item of “factor loading” and Fornell and Larcker (1981) designated items with loading, he labeled that the values which are equal or higher than 0.7 will be considered as

excellent, equal or higher than 0.63 directed as very good, whereas equal or higher than 0.55 reflected as good values, else equal or higher than 0.45 will be considered as reasonable and equal or higher than 0.32 pondered as poor value. Below in the table 4.11, the indicator items can be seen with its cross loading in table format.

Fornell-Larcker Criterion:

Fornell-Larcker Criterion are the square-roots of AVE of each latent variable in a model which must be higher than the correlations and the higher value in any row or column represent the diagonals (Liengaard et al., 2020). Below in table 4.12 all the diagonal values can be seen.

	EP	TMX	TT	TW	TR
EP	0.818				
TMX	0.575	0.855			
TT	0.432	0.637	0.884		
TW	0.469	0.454	0.279	0.749	
TR	0.417	0.277	0.292	0.411	0.792

Collinearity Assessment:

Collinearity assessment defined as the correlation among the variables and it depicts the condition in which some of the independent variables are highly correlated in which it tends to expand the variance of at least one estimated regression coefficient. It is one of the important aspect of this analysis and Variance Inflation Factor or VIF indicates that the value which is equal or above 5 signify a problem (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). It is actually the volume of multicollinearity in a set of multiple regression variables. Whereas, below 3 or between 3 and 5 represent satisfactory. However, between 5 and 10 although show high correlation but its problematic in model fit. On the contrary, 1 represents no correlation among the variables. The table 4.13 display all the values of VIF.

Value of Structural Model (Hypothesis Testing), Model Fit:

Standardized Root Means Residual or SRMR can be defined as, “the measure of the mean absolute value of the covariance residuals” and regarding research the square-root is used for model fitness and SRMR helps to find the validation. Whereas, the variance measured through the SRMR which leads towards the outcomes of correlation and correlation matrix of a model (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The acceptable range of the SRMR is less than 0.08. So, the model has been accepted because SRMR is 0.074, which is quite good value and close to the threshold. d-ULS (The squared Euclidean distance) depends on eigenvalues and d-G (the Geodesic) display two methods of calculating the inconsistency. So, it must be higher than the original value of d-ULS and d-G fit criteria for a good fit. The value which $P > 0.05$ in Chi-Square depicts the reliable relationship among the variables, as it can be seen in the table 4.14 below that the value of Chi-Square is 1040.491. Or it can be said that if there is relationship among variables the frequencies will vary and the value of the Chi- Square will be large as well.

	Model Fit	
	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.074	0.074
d_ULS	2.366	2.366
d_G	0.946	0.946

Chi-Square	1040.491	1040.491
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Model & Hypotheses Testing

Tool (Smart PLS-SEM): Smart PLS as a software used in the measurement of model and structural model to evaluate rapidly and also to check the validity of convergence and discrimination, whereas the reliability of questionnaire was also been examined by applying Cronbach's Alpha reliability method (Silaparasetti, Rao, & Khan, 2017). The reliability coefficient of the questionnaire is higher than 0.7 (Hair, Anderson, Babin, & Black, 2010).

Two or more endogenous and exogenous variables' relationship can be measured through PLS-SEM (Hair Jr, Matthews, Matthews, & Sarstedt, 2017). This software is mostly used to test the dependent and independent variables instantaneously to analyze sample with skewness and even the small data sets in the social sciences which further assist in bargaining the interdependencies of the relationships of variables (Lu, Guo, Qian, He, & Xu, 2015). Else it has gained a huge popularity within few years just because of its methods of validity and reliability with statistical power approach (Hair Jr et al., 2017). The internal model consist of dependent and independent variables to build the relationship among them, whereas indicators indicates the outer model with the latent variables (Wong, 2013). Teamwork, Team trust and Training were taken as the Independent variables and their indicators are attached with them. Whereas, EP has been taken as Dependent Variable. However, Team Member Exchange or TMX function as stimulating moderator.

Measurement Model: As, according to the third chapter's theoretical framework has been drawn in Smart PLS named as model. Whereas, the constructs as Latent variables were drawn and these variables were Teamwork, Team trust and Training with the addition of indicators to their particular latent variables. Teamwork had 10 indicators, Team trust with four indicators and Training had five indicators. However, the moderator variable was also added i.e. TMX with its six indicators as well.

Hypotheses Testing: The "bootstrapping method" was done on the employed sample which was two hundred and ten in numbers to find out the coefficients of hypothesis. After testing through the PLS-SEM as endorsed, the results were obtained of the model (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The results clearly display in the table-form after running bootstrapping successively showing the information about the direct or inverse relationship and the proportional strengths of Independent variable on that of dependent variable. It hinge on the path coefficient, if it is high than the impact of independent variable on dependent variable is high. Likewise, if the T-value is above than 1.96 and P-value is lower than 0.05, it depicts significant relationship which means that the outcomes was 95% perfect (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

According to this research, Team Member Exchange or TMX playing role as moderator which was calculated by the method of "moderation by interaction terms". First of all, the relationship of moderator and Independent variables were checked by multiplying and then with the dependent variable evaluated as a whole. However, the outcomes can be seen in the table below.

So, the outcome of the hypothesis testing. It also display that TMX as a moderator signifies only with two independent variables other than the training. As, the P-Value of all the relationships are less than 0.05 excluding TR*TMX->EP, the P-Value of this relation is 0.328 which depicts no relationship among them. Else the T-Value of all the relationships of

variables in table is higher than 1.96 excluding TR*TMX->EP which depicts no relationship among them.

Path Coefficients						
		Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
TR*TMX	->	-0.070	-0.027	0.071	0.977	0.328
Employee Performance						
TT*TMX	->	0.271	0.242	0.099	2.753	0.006
Employee Performance						
TW*TMX	->	0.185	0.204	0.091	2.042	0.041
Employee Performance						
Team Member Exchange	->	0.341	0.347	0.068	5.035	0.000
Employee Performance						
Team trust	->	0.292	0.235	0.103	2.832	0.005

Employee Performance Teamwork	->	0.190	0.195	0.064	2.955	0.003
Employee Performance Training	->	0.136	0.140	0.059	2.287	0.022

Total Direct & Indirect Effect:

To check the indirect effects without moderator, the test has been done and the results were TW has a significant positive relationship with the EP in the same way TT has significant positive relationship with EP and as well as TR also has significant positive relationship with that of EP. As their P-Values are less than 0.05 and the T-Values are greater than 1.96. Whereas, we can be seen the tabl2 4.16 that, TMX or Team Member Exchange moderates between the relationships of TW with EP, TT with EP and TR with EP, these were three hypothesis H4, H5 and H6. The P-Value of H4 and H5 were less than 0.05 and T-Value is greater than 1.96 which depicts that the relationships are significantly positive. But the P-Value of H6 was in negative i.e. -0.070 and T-Value was less than 1.96 which depicts that there was no relationship among them, the TMX in this hypothesis does not affect the relationship of TR with EP so this hypothesis was rejected.

Coefficient of determination (R-Square):

R-square shows the ability of the theoretical model’s prognostication and the dependency of R-square on exogenous variables. 0-1 is the specific or stipulated range of R-square (Hair Jr et al., 2017). The value of the R-square define the relationship between variables as strong, medium or weak. Whereas, 0.25 signify weak coefficient, 0.5 and 0.7 signify moderate coefficient (Hu & Bentler, 1999). As, according to the results which can be seen in table 4.17 is 42.9% variation is illuminated by the inputs of the variable.

R Square	R Square	R Square Adjusted
	0.429	0.418

Sr.	Hypothesis	Relationships	Path Coefficients	P-value	T-value	Decision
H1	Teamwork has significant positive effect on the employee performance.	TW -> EP	0.190	0.003	2.832	Accepted
H2	Team trust has momentous positive effect on employee performance.	TT -> EP	0.292	0.005	2.287	Accepted

H3	Training has significant positive effect on employee performance.	TR-> EP	0.136	0.022	2.955	Accepted
H4	TMX has significant positive effect on the relationship of teamwork and employee performance.	TW*TMX -> EP	0.185	0.041	2.042	Accepted
H5	TMX has significant positive effect on the relationship of team trust and employee performance.	TT*TMX -> EP	0.271	0.006	2.753	Accepted
H6	TMX has significant positive effect on the relationship of training and employee performance.	TR*TMX -> EP	-0.070	0.328	0.977	Rejected

SMART PLS MODEL

Discussion:

The 1st objective of this study was to analyze the effect of teamwork on employee performance, the effect of team trust on employee performance and training on employee performance. The results displays that teamwork has positive impact on the employee performance (O=0.190 and T=2.955), whereas Team trust has positive impact on the employee performance (O=0.292 and T=2.832), and Training also exhibit that it has a positive effect on the employee performance as well (O=0.136 and T=2.287) in SME's of Pakistan. In the end, the effect of TMX was also positive effect on employee performance (O=0.341 and T=5.035). The moderating effect of TMX between the teamwork and employee performance was positive (O=0.185 and T=2.042), the moderating effect of TMX between Team trust and employee performance was also positive (O=0.271 and T=2.753), but the moderating effect of TMX between Training and employee performance was negative (O=-0.070 and T=0.977) which depicts that the relationship between training and employee performance is positive in nature but TMX do not have any relationship with them or it neither effect their relationship.

Hence, the positive relationships of teamwork, team-trust and training with employee performance depicts that the SME's operate a number of small and large ventures which include many different teams. Definitely, teamwork, team trust and training helps employees to grow which further benefit them to improve their performance supplementary it's an advantage for organizational development which leads towards in the economic growth of a country. Those who prefer to work alone, they are unable to grow faster as compare to any good team member, on the contrary people who work as team member and trust them they learn more from their team members through exchanging knowledge with each other and trusting each other. These teams complete their target on time or before time. People who work in teams are also widely-open to different skills and competencies by their team members. They share different ideas, through brainstorming they tend to create novelty in their work and learning from other's mistakes as well. Due to teamwork, team-trust in the teams these all together tends towards the competitive advantage of the organization.

Actually, this is the easiest effective way to flow information among the team members which play a vital role in converting information into the knowledge. Briefly, Teamwork and team-trust can results positively growth for both individually and organizationally as well. As it was said by the Haber (2016) that, teamwork can accomplish good outcomes at individual level and as well as organizational level, the employees of the organization must believe in the contribution on their behalf towards the organization and do not take it for-granted.

Hence, the Hypothesis H1 as Teamwork have significant positive effect on the employee performance, H2 as Team trust have momentous positive effect on employee performance, H3 as Training have significant positive effect on employee performance, H4 as TMX has significant positive effect on the relationship of teamwork and employee performance and H5 as TMX has significant positive effect on the relationship of team trust and employee performance have positive relationships been accepted. But on the contrary H6 have negative relationship, as the TMX do not have positive effect on the relationship of training and employee performance. So, H6 have been rejected. H4 and H5 indicate that TMX (Team Member Exchange) play vital as moderator.

Theoretical Implications:

This study prolongs the generalizability of the positive relationships between teamwork and employee performance, team-trust and employee performance, else training and employee performance to the SME's of Pakistan. Furthermore, it also discusses that the relationships of teamwork with employee performance and team-trust with employee performance strengthens for those people who trust their team members and share knowledge with them and collaborate within teams through teamwork. However, relationship with TMX as moderator are very much new empirical findings in the research context because this report is pioneer in its nature in developing country like Pakistan. It will help researchers to think further to open many other ways to research. While hiring the employees, it must be consider that these employees are team players and believe in team member exchange phenomena and who should be adequately supported by the team members which leads to high level of positivity in employee performance. Perhaps if the employee have less support from the team members they would not be able to perform well which will results in low employee performance. This study helps in improving EP which leads to improvement in organizational performance and further benefits in generating more revenue. Due to the implication of these findings in the SME's by the managers, teams will be motivated to work beyond the boundary as compared to aloof environment as the interaction among team members show keen interest and will help in emerging the novel ideas and performing them practically. In this way, it will definitely impact the improvement in productivity. And healthy work environment for the employees within teams and organization will develop them to grow efficiently. The results of this research can be utilize by the management of SME's in developing countries like Pakistan. And these results can practice for future studies, it will further open new doors for the researchers and scholars to look forward.

Limitations & Future Research Recommendation:

The limitation must need to be considered, firstly as, the study was limited and focused only on the quantitative research approach, for future research as it can be study through the qualitative research method or mix method approach as well. Secondly, this study was also emphasis only cross sectional study, it can be study as longitudinal for better results. Thirdly, the study was limited till Pakistan which only contain one of the under developing countries, the horizon can be expand to other under-developed countries or shall be replicated in different geographical locations. Fourthly, the restricted time span of four to five months was also the reason to limitize the research. Fifth, in this study the sample size was only 210 under limited time period, in case of large sample size the results would give better prediction as primary data research require more time as compared to secondary data collection. Sixth, there can be other margin conditions as well which can be study, may strengthen the positive relationships of Teamwork, team-trust and training with employee performance includes Ostracism, LMX and climate of informality as moderators.

Conclusion:

In 21st century, more and more attention is given towards research on the SME's and trying to gain competitive edge or competitive advantage through improving employee performance. Now a days organizations strongly believe in it human capital and also prefer

to invest on their employees for the development of not only on personal performance but also for the evolution of organizations which leads towards the economic growth of countries. SME's who have better TMX, will eventually have better employee performance which may results in Competitive edge on others. This study makes a trivial effort to the theoretical relationship of teamwork with employee performance, team-trust with employee performance and training with employee performance and team member exchange together in one empirical study particularly in the perspective of SME's in Pakistan. Even now a days organizations are considering highly the phenomena of employee performance as it is the most important and very serious issue of in SME's due to competition in the market and computer-integrated manufacturing (CIM) technologies. Moreover, it has been argued from few years that employees must consider to work in team and organization's need to contribute in developing teams, as this phenomena particularly subsidize in the organizations in gaining sustainable competitive advantage in the market.

This study highlights how TMX or team member exchange effect the relationships of teamwork on employee performance, team-trust on employee performance and training on employee performance according to 210 employees working in SME's in the environment of competition currently in Pakistan. The results shows that TMX or team member exchange is fully moderating the relationship of teamwork with employee performance and team-trust with employee performance. On the contrary, the relationship between training and employee performance is positive but TMX or team member exchange do not moderate within this relationship as the value of original sample (O) =-0.070 which is negative in nature and -0.027 and P-Value is 0.328 which depicts not relationship of TMX among them.

The conclusion may help organizations in this era to understand that team member exchange is also an essential part of teams which supplementary enhance the employee performance and enrich teamwork within teams as a result. These results additionally essential to understand the worth of teamwork, team-trust, training and team member exchange in organizational development for future. Establishing an organizational culture to maximize the performance of the employees by using their potentials in meaningful methods can be a huge contribution. We can also conclude that, Extensive trainings can adversely affect the employee performance when moderated by TMX within teams in SME's as a result in our study. List of population used for this study had only 1000 SME's, we suggest to use the broader and different geographically located SME's in future e.g. other developing countries. At the end, we can believe that this research will open new boulevards for basic and applied research in other business sectors of Pakistan and as well as in other under-developed countries.

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